

LAMINATES WITH UNDER/OVER LACING MADE BY AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, procedures to make triaxial composite laminates by Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) are introduced. The influence of the procedure on the deformation of the final laminate is shown. A few mechanical properties for two types of tow-interlacing laminates made by AFP are determined and compared with those of traditional unidirectional layer laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials grows rapidly in many industries especially in aerospace and automobile. Fabric architectures give composite laminates certain interesting characteristics compared with traditional unidirectional layer composites such as higher impact resistance, and more balanced in-plane properties. On the other hand, the need to increase the speed of production, and the need to make larger structures require that automated manufacturing be used. In automated composite manufacturing techniques such as automated fiber placement (AFP), or automated tape lay up (ATL), unidirectional tows or tapes are used. It is difficult to feed fabrics into these machines. Recently, a new concept to make laminates with interlacing tows was proposed and patented by M. H. Nagelsmit et al [1] [2]. Laminates made using this concept are called AP-PLY laminates. The AP-PLY laminates show improvement in impact damage tolerance. Depending on the pattern, the compression after impact (C.A.I) strength increases by 5-10%. Moreover, by using AP-PLY pattern, mode I and mode II fracture toughnesses show increase of 89% and 20% respectively. The AP-PLY developed in [1, 2] are mainly biaxial weaves (plain weave or satin weaves). Extending this methodology, this paper proposes a method to make triaxial composite laminates by AFP. It also presents results of some in-plane mechanical properties for two types of AP-PLY laminates.

2 MATERIAL AND EQUIPMENT

This research uses unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg with CYCOM 977-2 epoxy resin system, the tow width is 0.25 inch. This material is provided by Cytec Solvay Group. AFP machine used is a six axis fiber placement system from Automated Dynamics. Mechanical tests were conducted on the 100 KN MTS Testing Machine.

3 AP-PLY TRIAXIAL COMPOSITES MADE BY AFP

Triaxial weave fabrics were invented by Norris Dow in 1969 [3]. For this fabric, instead of having interlacing in two orientations as in biaxial fabrics, the triaxial fabrics have tows' interlacing in three directions. Laminates using triaxial fabrics impregnated with resin are called triaxial weave fabric composites. Figure 1 shows a few different patterns of triaxial fabric laminates. It can have either hexagonal empty space, no empty space or triangular empty space. Most of the times, triaxial fabric laminates are manufactured with only one layer consisting three different fiber orientations. Triaxial fabrics composites show some interesting properties compared with biaxial woven composites. First of all they provide more isotropic behavior [4]. Secondly, along with the increase of biaxial stress, resistance to shear of triaxial fabrics composites increases while that of biaxial woven composites decreases [4]. This is because of yarn interlacing with one another at 60 degree angles. One application of triaxial fabric laminates is the ultra-lightweight thin membrane antenna reflector of a spacecraft [5].

Figure 1. Some patterns of 0/60/-60 triaxial fabric laminates a) Hexagon empty space, b) no empty space, c) triangle empty space [3]

Traditionally, triaxial fabrics composites are made by impregnating dry triaxial fabrics with resin and then curing in autoclave. Triaxial fabrics are manufactured by a complex weaving machine (Figure 2). In order to make triaxial composite laminates using simple AFP and unidirectional prepreg, the concept of AP-PLY laminates is applied.

Figure 2. Triaxial Weaving machine (TWM) Photo Courtesy from Triaxial Structure Inc. website [6]

The basic procedure to make triaxial fabric by AFP includes 6 steps (Figure 3). The materials deposited in each orientation are divided into two groups. n is defined as the number of tows skipped between two laid down tows in one group. Each step is the layup of one group. The procedure starts with the first group with 0° fiber orientation. The next group with the same fiber orientation (Group 4)

will be laid down after finishing the first groups of others fiber orientations (Group 2 (60°) and Group 3 (-60°)). Interlacing between two different fiber orientations forms the overlap region. Relative position between interlacing points of $0/60$ and $0/-60$ interlacing is defined by the distance d .

Figure 3. Basic procedure to make AP-PLY triaxial laminate

Depending on the layup pattern, different types of laminates can be created. Four different layup patterns were introduced in Figure 4. Some possible AP-PLY triaxial laminates with different n , and d are presented in Table 1.

AP-PLY triaxial laminate	Pattern	
	n	d
No-empty space laminate (Figure 4a)	1	0
Hexagonal empty space laminate (Figure 4b)	5	$2\sqrt{3}$
Triangular empty space laminate 1 (Figure 4c)	5	0
Triangular empty space laminate 2 (Figure 4d)	3	1

Table 1. Layup pattern for different AP-PLY triaxial laminates

Figure 4. Different patterns for AP-PLY Triaxial laminates a) No-empty space b) Hexagonal empty space c) Triangular empty space 1 d) Triangular empty space 2

Effect of symmetric and unsymmetric layup sequence

In this study, two no-empty space AP-PLY triaxial laminates were made ($n=1$; $d=0$). It is noted that all tows in two groups which are laid down the first and the last don't have interlacing but only a simple overlap. In order to reduce the number of non-interlacing tows, each group of tows as defined previously is divided into 2 sub-groups. Therefore, instead of having 6 groups, there are now 12 groups corresponding to 12 layup steps. There is a small difference in the procedures to make these

laminates, one is unsymmetric layup and the other is symmetric layup. In both cases, these 12 steps can be broken down into two cycles (Table 2). For type I laminates (unsymmetric laminates), the 0° layers are laid down at steps 1, 4, 7, 10, the 60° layers are laid down at steps 2,5, 8, 11, and the -60° layers are laid down at steps 3,6, 9, 12. For type I laminate, cycle 2 is a repeat of cycle 1 except that each type of tow is shifted away by one tow (for example rather than tow position 1, it is tow position 2). For type II laminates (symmetric laminates), the tows in cycle 2 are mirror images of the tows in cycle 1, across the mid plane of the laminate.

The results are shown in Figure 5. The unsymmetric laminates show distortion while the symmetric laminates do not. As such by choosing a proper layup sequence, flat triaxial weave laminates can be obtained.

	Layup procedure 1 (unsymmetric)	Layup procedure 2 (symmetric)	
CYCLE 1	Step 1	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 1	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 1
	Step 2	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 1	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 1
	Step 3	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 1	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 1
	Step 4	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 3	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 3
	Step 5	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 3	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 3
	Step 6	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 3	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 3
CYCLE 2	Step 7	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 2	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 2
	Step 8	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 2	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 2
	Step 9	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 2	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 2
	Step 10	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 4	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 4
	Step 11	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 4	60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 4
	Step 12	-60° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 4	0° direction; every fourth tows starting from tow number 4

Table 2. Unsymmetric and symmetric layup procedures for no-empty space AP-PLY Triaxial laminates

Figure 5. “Triaxial woven laminates” made by AFP
(a) unsymmetric weave (b) symmetric weave

4 QUASI-ISOTROPIC AP-PLY LAMINATES MADE BY AFP

In order to examine the mechanical properties of AP-PLY woven laminates made by AFP, quasi-isotropic AP-PLY laminates were made based on the traditional $[45/-45/0/90]_{2S}$ layup sequence. Their layup sequences can be defined as 4 blocks where each block contains layers in 4 directions. Two types of AP-PLY laminates were made (Type 1 and Type 2). The properties of these laminates are compared with those of traditional unidirectional layer laminates (Type Regular). One block of Type 1 layup is shown in Figure 6. In Type 1, one woven layer contains layers in 2 perpendicular directions (45/-45 or 0/90). The procedure to make one block of Type 2 layup laminates is shown in Figure 7. In this type, one woven layer contains layers in 4 directions. Odd numbered tows in directions 45, -45, 0, 90 were laid down before the starting of even numbered tows in those 4 directions.

After layup process, laminates were cured in an autoclave. Curing cycle for CYCOM 977-2 is shown in Figure 8. Temperature was ramped up from room temperature to 177°C in 60 minutes, and then it was maintained for 180 minutes. Applied pressure was 70 psi and vacuum was ON for the whole process.

Microscopy was used to examine the cross sections of laminates. Figure 9 shows the cross sections of Type Regular, Type 1 and Type 2 laminates respectively.

It is noted that the quantities of resin rich areas due to manufacturing is the least for Type Regular and the most for Type 2 laminates. In both types of woven laminates, resin rich areas caused by manufacturing process are mainly distributed at the intersection of “warp” and “weft” directions.

Figure 6. Procedure to make one block 45/-45/0/90 of Type 1 quasi-isotropic laminates

Figure 7. Procedure to make one block 45/-45/0/90 of Type 2 quasi-isotropic laminates

Figure 8. Curing cycle for CYCOM 977-2

Figure 9. Microscopic investigation of a) Type Regular (Unidirectional) b) Type 1 (Quasi isotropic) c) Type 2 laminates (Quasi isotropic)

When doing layup, skipped tows create empty channels. When tows in other directions cross these channels, they will be shifted down by the depth of the channel. This explains the fact that Type 2 has the highest fiber waviness where at some places, the empty space depth is 4 times of the tow thickness. Type Regular has the smallest fiber waviness because there is no empty channel created during layup.

5 MECHANICAL TESTS

Tensile and compressive tests were conducted on the samples cut from the laminates in section 4, following ASTM D3039 and D3410 respectively.

		Regular	Type 1	Type 2
Tensile	Modulus (GPa)	53.8	53.0	51.3
	Strength (MPa)	742.4	746.4	690.5
Compressive	Modulus (GPa)	46.1	46.5	45.2
	Strength (MPa)	627.9	637.5	603.6

Table 3. Tension and compression properties of three type of laminates

Table 3. shows the tensile test results. Type Regular and Type 1 laminates have almost the same value in tensile modulus and tensile strength. Compared to Type Regular laminates, Type 2 shows a slight reduction of tensile modulus (5%) and of tensile strength (7%). Since tensile properties depend mostly on fiber, this slight reduction can be explained by higher fiber waviness in the case of Type 2 laminates.

Similar trend was noted for compressive properties. Compressive modulus for Type Regular and Type 1 is 46.1 GPa and 46.5 GPa consequently while that of Type 2 is 45.2 GPa. Compressive strength of Type 2 laminate is 4% lower than the value of Type Regular samples.

Figure 10. Failure area after compression test

Failed samples of three types of laminates after compression test are presented in Figure 10. The failure modes of three types are different. For regular type, failure mode depends mostly on in-plane stress and fiber break through thickness while for Type 1 and Type 2 laminates, failure is by interlaminar delamination. More studies need to be done to understand the impact of tows interlacing on failure.

6 CONCLUSIONS

It was shown that by properly sequencing the order of depositing different tows along different directions, it is possible to make a variety of fabric laminates using automated composites manufacturing. The properties of these laminates can be varied depending on the sequencing arrangement. For triaxial fabric laminates, a slight change in the sequencing can result in either a warped laminate or a flat laminate. Procedures to make different types of AP-PLY triaxial laminates by AFP were proposed. No-empty space triaxial laminates are made with two different layup sequences. Symmetric layup sequence creates flat laminate while unsymmetric layup sequence ends up with a curve laminate. For the case of biaxial fabric laminates, the properties of the laminates also vary with the sequencing arrangement for the tows.

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